

KINETICS OF THE REACTION BETWEEN CHLORAL HYDRATE AND BROMINE

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The kinetics of the oxidation of chloral hydrate by bromine in aqueous solutions has been studied at 30° and 40°. The reaction has been found to take place according to the equation

The retarding influences of hydrogen and bromine ions on the velocity of reaction have been quantitatively studied. The energy of activation of the reaction has been found to be 15830 calories.

Bromine oxidises acetaldehyde to acetic acid in neutral solutions. In acid solutions, however, the reaction results in halogen substitution through a prototropic mechanism (Dawson, Burton and Ark, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, 105, 1275). Trichloroacetaldehyde which exists in aqueous solution exclusively as chloral hydrate, does not offer any scope for substitution. The compound chloral hydrate is itself acidic in character and in acid solutions the only possible reaction with bromine is oxidation. Ogialoro (*Ber.*, 1874, 7, 1461) reported that chloral, when heated with bromine, formed the acid bromide, CCl_3COBr . Chlorine and bromine have been shown to react photochemically with chloral, yielding a number of oxidation products (Schumacher *et al.*, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1939, **B44**, 57; 1940, **B47**, 67). Koltzoff (*Pharm. Weekblad*, 1923, **60**, 2) mentions that bromine does not oxidise chloral in acid solutions. It is well known that chloral hydrate molecule is stable only either in neutral or acid solutions and that alkaline solutions decompose rapidly (Enklaar, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1905, **24**, 419). Attempts to oxidise this compound keeping both the carbon atoms in tact should therefore be made only in neutral or acid solutions. Preliminary experiments carried out in this laboratory showed that chloral hydrate reacted with bromine at measurable speeds at ordinary temperature and in equimolecular proportions. The quantity of acid formed, when decolorisation of a known quantity of bromine in presence of excess of chloral hydrate took place, was found on estimation to be equal to what should be expected if the reaction had taken place quantitatively according to the equation

The quantity of bromine taken up by a given quantity of chloral hydrate was likewise found to conform to the above equation. That trichloroacetic acid was formed was further proved by the decomposition of the resulting solution on boiling, yielding chloroform and carbon dioxide. We have studied the kinetics of the reaction and the results are reported in this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL

Chemicals employed in this investigation were all of extra pure quality. The solutions were all prepared in redistilled water.

The reaction vessels were kept in an electrically regulated thermostat for all kinetic measurements. The reaction was followed by withdrawing definite volumes of reaction mixtures and estimating the unreacted bromine iodometrically.

Table I contains the results of an experiment carried out with a mixture containing 0.25 *M* chloral hydrate and 0.0054*N* bromine. The reaction mixture (10 c.c.) was titrated each time, after the addition of potassium iodide against *N*/200-thiosulphate.

TABLE I

Temp. = 30°.

Time.	Thio	$k_{uni.}$	Time.	Thio.	$k_{uni.}$
0 min.	11.90 c.c.				
15	9.30	0.01440	72	5.50 c.c.	0.01069
30	8.00	0.01320	91	4.60	0.01042
50	6.45	0.01221	121	3.80	0.009407
			160	3.00	0.00853

It will be seen that the unimolecular velocity constant falls off as the reaction progresses, more rapidly at the initial stages than at the later stages. This may be due, as is known in other cases of aqueous bromine oxidations, to the accumulation in the system of hydrogen and bromide ions and the retarding influence they exert. Tables II and III contain results of two experiments carried out to test the influence of each one of these two ions on the velocity of the reaction. Potassium bromide was added in one case and hydrochloric acid in the other, in such quantities that the concentrations of the bromine and the hydrogen ions in the respective mixtures could be regarded as constant through the course of the reaction. The concentrations of chloral hydrate and bromine were the same as in the previous experiment.

TABLE II

Temp. = 30°. KBr = 0.05*M*.

<i>t.</i>	Thio.	$k_{uni.}$
0 min.	10.90 c.c.	...
30	6.90	0.00907
46	7.40	0.008395
63	6.70	0.007705
87	6.70	0.007429
115	5.10	0.006578
188	3.60	0.005865

TABLE III

Temp. = 30°. Conc of HCl = 0.05*M*.

<i>t.</i>	Thio.	$k_{uni.}$
0 min.	13.50 c.c.	...
43	12.20	0.001736
85	11.45	0.001626
145	10.50	0.001548
234	9.20	0.001522
325	8.10	0.001488
455	6.85	0.001431

These results indicate that each of the ions, bromine and hydrogen, exerts powerful retarding influence, the effect of the hydrogen ion being more powerful. Each by itself is not sufficient to exert a steadying influence on the rate. The effect of the initial addition of sufficient excess of both potassium bromide and hydrochloric acid was next tried. The results are contained in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Temp. = 30° Chloral hydrate = 0.20 M. Bromine = 0.002854 N. HCl (initial) = 0.008 N. KBr (initial) = 0.0377 M. 25 c.c. titrated each time against N/400-thiosulphate.

<i>t</i> .	Thio.	<i>k</i> _{ant.}
0 min.	24.00 c.c.	
30	18.90	0.007951
45	16.70	0.008050
60	14.60	0.008027
75	13.15	0.008015
90	11.70	0.008000
121	9.20	0.007912

Mean 0.007993

The steady value of the velocity constant at the different stages of the reaction indicates clearly the role of the hydrogen and the bromine ions. The retarding influence of hydrogen ion is obviously due to the suppression of the ionisation of chloral hydrate and the consequent diminution of the effective concentration of the anion which appears to be the real reactant, in accordance with the equation,

Similarly, the bromine ion diminishes the effective concentration of free bromine by forming the tribromide ion according to the equation,

The order of the reaction with respect to chloral hydrate was determined by a set of experiments in which the initial concentration of this constituent was altered, while those of others were kept constant. Table V shows the variation of the velocity constant with increase in the concentration of chloral hydrate.

TABLE V

HCl = 0.01 N. KBr = 0.02 M. Bromine = 0.002 N.

Chloral hydrate (M)	...	0.05	0.10	0.15	0.20	0.25
<i>k</i> × 10 ⁴	...	10.42	21.42	31.05	39.15	49.45

These results indicate, considering that it is the ion of chloral hydrate that is involved, the unimolecularity of the process with respect to chloral hydrate. The reaction can therefore be represented by the equation,

Influence of Hydrogen-ion Concentration

We chose sulphuric acid for the addition of hydrogen ion in all subsequent experiments as the addition of hydrochloric acid might introduce a complication by the formation of chloro-dibromide ion (Ray, this *Journal*, 1934, 11, 117).

Table VI contains results of a detailed study of the retarding influence of hydrogen ion.

TABLE VI

Chloral hydrate = 0.25 M. KBr = 0.10 M. Bromine = 0.0025N.

Equiv. of H ₂ SO ₄ per litre	0.008	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.04	0.05	0.06
$k \times 10^4$	30.21	27.40	15.64	11.10	9.20	7.52	6.36

There is a progressive diminution in the velocity constant, as is to be expected if the anion is the reactant, with increase in the initial concentration of hydrochloric acid.

The concentration of the anion could be reckoned on the assumption that chloral hydrate behaves like a weak acid, HA, in the following way

where K_a represents the dissociation constant of the acid and HA, the concentration of the unionised acid. From which we can deduce

$$\text{A}^- = \frac{K_a \cdot (\text{HA})}{K_a + \text{H}^+}, \text{ where } (\text{HA}) \text{ is the total concentration of chloral hydrate.}$$

Introducing this in the kinetic expression,

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = k \cdot \text{CA}^- \times \text{C}_{\text{Br}_2} = \frac{k \cdot K_a \cdot (\text{HA})}{\text{H}^+ + K_a} \times \text{C}_{\text{Br}_2}$$

= $k_{\text{obs}} \times \text{C}_{\text{Br}_2}$ for concentrations (HA) large in comparison with C_{Br_2}

k_{obs} , the observed unimolecular velocity constant being equal to

$$\frac{k \cdot (\text{A}) \cdot K_a}{\text{H}^+ + K_a} = \frac{k' \cdot K_a}{\text{H}^+ + K_a} \quad \text{or} \quad \frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \frac{1}{k'} + \frac{\text{H}^+}{k' \times K_a}$$

This equation demands that we should get a straight line if we plot $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ against $H^+[H_2SO_4/2]$. Actually we get a very good straight line with an intercept on the $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ axis which should be equal to $1/k'$. $1/k' = 1.20 \times 10^3$ and the slope of the line $1/k'K_a = 2.416 \times 10^4$ from which K_a comes out to be equal to 4.96×10^{-8} .

This value for the Ostwald constant for chloral hydrate would mean that chloral hydrate is a fairly strong acid. Chloral hydrate, even on very careful purification is definitely acidic in its reaction towards litmus and should be expected to be so by virtue of the two hydroxyl groups attached to the same carbon atom. But one could hardly believe that it could be as strong as monochloroacetic acid ($K = 1.53 \times 10^{-3}$).

The molecular conductivity of chloral hydrate in 0.01 M solution is just 0.60 (Enklaar, *loc. cit.*) and it is a little difficult to reconcile this low conductivity with the high dissociation constant we arrive at on the basis of our kinetic study. We are investigating this matter further but we have to content ourselves at present by recording the observation we have made.

Influence of Bromine Ion on the Reaction Rate

The velocity of reaction, as observed before, is affected very considerably by the presence of bromide ion. This is obviously due to the removal of bromine from its free state by the formation of tribromide ion. The results of the experiments carried out at 30° and 40° with different concentrations of potassium bromide in the reaction mixtures are given in Table VII.

TABLE VII

Chloral hydrate = 0.20M. $H_2SO_4 = 0.01N$. Bromine = 0.0025N.

KBr.	$k_{30} \times 10^3$.	$k_{40} \times 10^3$.	k_{40}/k_{30} .	$\left[k_{\text{obs } 30} \times \frac{k_{30} + Br}{k_{20}} \right]$.	$\left[k_{\text{obs } 40} \times \frac{k_{40} + Br}{k_{40}} \right]$.
0.025 M	4.439	10.56	2.38	5.944	13.20
0.050	3.496	5.72	2.445	5.870	13.09
0.075	2.921	7.61	2.606	5.890	13.31
0.100	2.530	6.76	2.671	5.961	13.51
0.125	2.127	5.96	2.800	5.731	13.41
				Mean 5.879	13.304
				From graph $k' = 5.888$	13.510

The velocity constant falls off with increase in concentration of bromide ion. The equilibrium equation

$$K = \frac{(Br_2)_{\text{free}} \times Br^-}{Br_3^-} \quad \text{leads to the equation}$$

$$Br_2_{\text{free}} = \frac{K}{K + Br} \times Br_2_{\text{total}} \quad \text{expressing } Br_2_{\text{total}} = Br_2_{\text{free}} + Br_3^-.$$

The rate of reaction is proportional to the concentration of free bromine. Substituting this value for free bromine in the differential equation, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dx}{dt} &= k \cdot C_{A^-} \times C_{Br_2 \text{ free}} \\ &= k \cdot C_{A^-} \times \frac{K}{K + Br^-} \times C_{Br_2 \text{ total}} \\ k'' \cdot \frac{K}{K + Br^-} \times C_{Br_2 \text{ total}} &\text{ where } k'' = K \cdot C_{A^-} \text{ (} C_{A^-} \text{ being in large excess).} \end{aligned}$$

$k_{obs} \cdot C_{Br_2 \text{ total}}$ (k_{obs} being the observed unimolecular constant) therefore

$$\begin{aligned} k_{obs} &= k'' \cdot \frac{K}{K + Br^-} \quad \text{and} \\ \frac{1}{k_{obs}} &= \frac{1}{k''} + \frac{Br^-}{k'' \cdot K} \end{aligned}$$

As should be expected from this equation we get very good straight lines on plotting $1/k_{obs}$ against Br^- (KBr) at both the temperatures.

We get this inspite of the fact that we have employed concentrations of potassium bromide instead of activities of bromide ion. The intercept $1/k''$ at 30° has a value of 1.70×10^4 or $k'' = 5.888 \times 10^3$ and the slope $1/k'' \cdot K_{30} = 23.0 \times 10^4$ from which we get $K_{30} = 0.07380$. Similarly $1/k''$ at 40° gives 0.74×10^4 or $k'' = 13.510 \times 10^3$ and $1/k'' \cdot K_{40} = 0.74 \times 10^6$ from which $K_{40} = 0.100$.

The values for K appear to be somewhat higher than what should be expected from the figures given by Linhart (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1918, 40, 158). The values for

$k'' = k_{obs} \cdot \frac{K + Br^-}{K}$ calculated from the observed velocity constants at different concen-

trations of potassium bromide are included in the 5th and 6th vertical columns of Table VII. The constancy at both temperatures is good and the average values agree very well with the intercepts from graphs.

Temperature Coefficient of the Reaction Rate

Attention might here be drawn to the ratios $k'_{(obs)40} / k_{(obs)30}$ given in the 4th column of Table VII which show a steady rise with increase in the concentration of the retardant. This increase in temperature coefficient, signifying increase in energy of activation (which should be considered apparent energy of activation) is understandable as we know that the observed velocity constant involves the variable, concentration of bromide ion. The correct basis for the calculation of temperature coefficient is the value of k'' .

$$\frac{k''_{40}}{k''_{30}} = \frac{13.510}{5.888} = 2.294.$$

The energy of activation calculated from this value of temperature coefficient comes out to be 15830 cal. Similarly, the temperature coefficient of the equilibrium constant for the reaction

from the values of K , deduced from our measurements, leads to the value 5786 calories for the heat of reaction.

D I S C U S S I O N

The results recorded in the paper indicate the reaction to be comparatively simple and straight forward. The equation

correctly represents the reaction kinetically and stoichiometrically. The process of oxidation consists in the removal of two hydrogen atoms from the chloral hydrate ion, as hydrobromic acid.

One of the hydrogen atoms is the hydroxyl hydrogen, ordinarily somewhat remotely situated from the other hydrogen which is directly linked to the carbon atom. The point of interest therefore is to account for the simultaneous removal of these hydrogens by an activated collision with a bromine molecule. Such removal could be facilitated only in case where the two hydrogens are situated in sufficient proximity to one another in such a manner that a bromine molecule colliding in suitable orientation could contact both. It is interesting to recall in this context, the structure proposed for chloral hydrate by Werner long ago (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, 88, 1376) to account for the formation of chloroform and formic acid from this molecule

and compare it with the structure arrived at by Davies (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1940, 36, 333) on the basis of infra-red studies.

The only apparent difference between the two, as depicted on paper, is in regard to the disposition of the hydrogen atom directly attached to the carbon atom. The infra-red evidence is that the hydroxyl hydrogens are clamped towards the chlorines joined to the α -carbon atom. If we consider the actual locations of the three hydrogens in space with the hydroxyl hydrogens so clamped, it would be found that the

distance between the directly linked hydrogen and any one of the two hydroxyl hydrogens is small enough to enable a bromine molecule getting in between them to contact both. Hence, in the chloral hydrate ion, in which there is only one hydroxyl hydrogen, the simultaneous removal of this and the directly linked hydrogen by a single energised collision with a bromine molecule is possible, provided that the energy conditions are satisfied.

The energy of activation is of the magnitude usually met with in simple bimolecular reactions, indicating the effectiveness of a good number of collisions and consequently the facility with which the reaction seems to proceed.

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